

Organoiridium Complexes containing *N*-Heterocycles—A Review

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A great majority of the organoiridium complexes containing *N*-heterocycles reported so far are four-coordinate. Many of these are associated with either cyclic diolefins or CO. Nmr spectroscopy has been widely used for the structural elucidation of the complexes. In several of the cases, the mono-, bi- and polynuclear nature has been established by crystal structure studies. A few of the complexes have been shown to possess catalytic activity.

In the recent past there has been a phenomenal progress in the area of organorhodium complexes containing *N*-heterocycles whereas the corresponding organoiridium systems have received scarce attention. Nevertheless, the latter are of considerable interest from the point of view of catalytic¹, anticancer²⁻⁵, antineoplastic^{6,7} activities as well as photochemical⁸ and liquid crystalline⁹ properties. Their known catalytic activities include conversion of inexpensive raw materials into valuable fuels¹⁰, photochemical activation of carbonmonoxide and water¹¹ as well as formate¹², photoelectrochemical generation of hydrogen¹³ and electrochemical hydride transfer in presence of cyclohexanone¹⁴ or pyridine nucleotides^{15,16}. Attention has also been paid towards the development of macromolecular iridium chelates¹⁷ with a view to prepare efficient polymeric catalysts that could serve as electroactive coatings and photoconducting materials¹⁸ as well as electroconducting and photochemical energy storage systems¹⁹. The present survey is restricted to the isolation and characterisation of complexes of iridium containing *N*-heterocycle(s) and carbon monoxide and/or a diene or a similar π -system. Special features of interest, if any, of these compounds have also been highlighted. The review is considered under two headings : (i) mononuclear complexes and (ii) bi- and polynuclear complexes.

Mononuclear complexes

Diene complexes :

Complexes of the type $[\text{Ir}(\mu\text{-X})(\text{L-L})_2]$; (X = Cl, Br; L-L = diolefin) undergo halobridge cleavage in presence of monodentate (Q) or bidentate (N-N)

N-heterocycle in refluxing ethanol or an appropriate solvent to afford mononuclear, neutral or ionic complexes. Tables 1 and 2 compile diverse types of organoiridium compounds isolated by several workers. The intense colours of some of the dichroic complexes cover the visible region and this property has been attributed to Ir–Ir stacking interactions³³.

Ramesh *et al.*²³ characterised five-coordinate complexes of the type $[\text{Ir}(\text{COD})(\text{biq})\text{X}]$ (X = Cl, Br) isolated as dark coloured crystals by the halobridge cleavage of $[\text{Ir}(\mu\text{-X})(\text{COD})_2]$ with N–N in a suitable solvent under reflux. Uson *et al.*²⁹ isolated a neutral red coloured complex $[\text{Ir}(\text{COD})(\alpha\text{-pybzt})]$ by reacting $[\text{Ir}(\text{COD})(\text{acac})]$ with $\alpha\text{-pybztH}$ in CH_2Cl_2 . On the other hand, the chlorobridge splitting of $[\text{Ir}(\mu\text{-Cl})(\text{COD})_2]$ by the *N*-heterocycle in presence of AgClO_4 affords dark violet crystals of $[\text{Ir}(\text{COD})(\alpha\text{-pybztH})]\text{ClO}_4$.

Siedle *et al.*³⁴ isolated $[\text{IrCl}(\text{COD})(\text{Phz})]$ (1) as dark brown needles by the bridge cleavage reaction of $[\text{Ir}(\mu\text{-Cl})(\text{COD})_2]$ with Phz in CH_2Cl_2 . The ¹H nmr spectrum of complex 1 reveals deshielded periprotons of Phz whose resonance occurs at δ 9.8 (d, ³J_{HH} 9 Hz). The deshielding in the *N*-heterocycle consequent to coordination has been attributed to the diamagnetic interaction of the protons, H_xH_y with Ir-5d₂ electrons.

It has been shown by Zassinovich *et al.*²⁰ that the substitution of coordinated diene in iridium(I) complexes by nitrogen heterocycles is not facile. For instance, attempts to synthesise $[\text{Ir}(\text{N-N})_2]^+$ (N–N = bipy, phen) from $[\text{Ir}(\text{COD})(\text{N-N})]^+$ and N–N were unsuccessful³⁵. It has been inferred that the

presence of diolefin as a non-labile ligand is necessary to stabilise the +1 oxidation state of the metal in these species.

TABLE 1—MONONUCLEAR NEUTRAL COMPLEXES OF THE TYPE $[\text{IrX}(\text{L-L})(\text{Q/N-N})]$

Diolefin L-L	N-Heterocycle Q/(N-N)	X	Ref.
COD COT NBD	py, mod, aqn, vin-py subs. phen	Cl	20
NBD	pip	Cl, Br, I	21
COD	phCH ₂ imd _z	Cl	22
COD	pmaa	Cl	9
COD	biq	Cl, Br	23
COD TFB	dpa	—	24
COD TFB Me ₃ TFB	tpzm	Cl	25
COD	R-bzIH	Cl	26
COD	a-pybzt	—	29

Ramaswamy *et al.*²⁶ have recently synthesised mononuclear complexes corresponding to the composition $[\text{IrCl}(\text{COD})(\text{R-bzIH})]$ (R = alkyl) by the chlorobridge splitting of the dimer $[\text{Ir}(\mu\text{-Cl})\text{COD}]_2$ with 2-substituted-benzimidazoles in acetone. Treatment of the mononuclear complexes with PPh₃ in presence of NaClO₄ affords cationic species of the type $[\text{Ir}(\text{COD})(\text{PPh}_3)(\text{R-bzIH})]\text{ClO}_4$. The latter are characterised by nmr and mass spectral studies³⁶. The ¹H, ¹³C nmr spectral features of $[\text{IrCl}(\text{COD})(\text{i-prbzIH})]$ (**2**) in CDCl₃ suggest the presence of conformers in solution. The preferred orientation of the isopropyl substituent in one of the conformers, apparently caused by steric effect, is manifested in the anomalous shielding of the methyl

protons which resonate at $\delta -0.28$ (d). That the cause of upfield shift seems to be due to steric reasons is corroborated by the absence of conformers in the carbonyl analogue. The orientation of the isopropylbenzimidazole moiety in

TABLE 2—MONONUCLEAR IONIC COMPLEXES OF THE TYPE $[\text{Ir}(\text{L-L})(\text{Q,Q'/N-N})]^{\pm} \text{X}^{\mp}$

L-L	Q/N-N	X	Ref.
COD	RbzIH, PPh ₃	ClO ₄	26
COD		Cl	20
COT NBD	aqn, dpk or subs. phen	PF ₆ ⁻ ClO ₄ ⁻	
COD	dpa	ClO ₄	24
COD, NBD TFB, Me ₃ TFB	tpzm	Cl ClO ₄	25
COD, NBD, TFB	indzH	$[\text{RhCl}_2(\text{COD})]\text{ClO}_4$	32
COD	py, Pcy ₃	PF ₆	27
COD	tcnbiimzt	K, Na Li, NEt ₄	28
COD	a-pybzIH	ClO ₄	29
COD	mpy, py, nmQn, Qn, dcQn	BF ₄ , ClO ₄	30
C ₅ Me ₅	bipy, phen	Cl	8
C ₅ Me ₅	biimztH ₂ , bithz	Cl	31

complex **2** relative to the square-plane around the metal in one of the dispositions could be expected to move the methyls of the isopropyl group into the shielding zone of the coordinated olefinic unit lying *trans* to the halogen, and a consequent restricted rotation. Similar observations have been made in the spectrum of the bromo analogue except that the methyl protons are shielded to a lesser extent due to the lower electronegativity of Br. DNMR studies have ruled out the possibility of fluxional behaviour but have favoured the coexistence of conformers. However, such a behaviour has not been observed in the rhodium³⁶ analogue despite the comparable ionic radii of the metal ions. This unusual behaviour of the isopropyl substituent of the N-heterocycle in an organometallic complex is apparently a first observation.

Danopoulos *et al.*³⁷ isolated paramagnetic complexes $[\text{Ir}(\text{mes})_2\text{L}_2]$ (L = py, Bu^tpy) as yellow green precipitates by the addition of excess of L to a solution of $[\text{Ir}(\text{mes})_2(\text{SEt}_2)]$ in ether. The epr spectrum of the complex $[\text{Ir}(\text{mes})_2\text{py}_2]$ in toluene at

77 K features three *g*-values confirming +2 oxidation state for the metal ion. Muller and

Friedrich³⁸ isolated $[(\text{Chd})_2\text{Ir}(2\text{-Nmpy})]$ (**3**) by reacting $[(\text{Chd})_2\text{IrCl}]$ with *N*-methylpyrrole in THF

and *N*-butyl lithium in hexane at -40° . The Ir-C binding is reflected in the ^1H nmr spectral profile of the complex taken in CD_2Cl_2 . Treatment of butadiene with an ethanolic solution of H_2IrCl_6 under reflux affords a compound which on subsequent reaction with py or mpy yields complex **4**³⁹.

According to Ladwig and Kaim¹, $[(\text{C}_5\text{Me}_5)\text{Ir}(\text{bipy})\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}$ on treatment with tetrabutyl ammonium tetrahydridoborate in dry THF at -20° yields a deep purple air-sensitive complex $[(\text{C}_5\text{Me}_5)\text{Ir}(\text{bipy})]$ (**5**). The latter being coordinatively unsaturated is electron-rich and has been postulated as an intermediate in the homogenous photocatalysis of

water gas shift reaction^{40,41}. Cyclic voltammetric, uv-vis, ^1H and ^{13}C nmr spectroscopic measurements of the complex in aprotic and protic solvents have revealed the electronic structures of neutral $[(\text{C}_5\text{Me}_5)\text{Ir}(\text{bipy})]$ and the cationic species $[(\text{C}_5\text{Me}_5)\text{IrH}(\text{bipy})]^+$.

Leipoldt *et al.*⁴² carried out the kinetic studies of substitution of $[\text{Ir}(\beta\text{-diket})(\text{COD})]$ with the derivatives of bipy, phen (N-N) in acetone to obtain five-coordinated carbon bonded β -diketonate complex $[\text{Ir}(\beta\text{-diket}-\text{C}^3)(\text{N}-\text{N})(\text{COD})]$. The rate constant for $[\text{Ir}(\text{acac})(\text{COD})(\text{bipy})]$ ($116 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 25°) has been found to be higher than that of the phen analogue ($13.6 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 25°) and this has been attributed to the lower rigidity of former heterocycle despite the basicities ($\text{p}K_a$) and steric effects of the two *N*-donors being of the same order. Ion-pairs of the type $[\text{Ir}(\text{COD})(\text{pic})_2]^+[\text{IrCl}_2(\text{CO})_2]^-$, $[\text{Ir}(\text{COD})(\text{tpzm})]^+[\text{RhCl}_2(\text{COD})]^-$ and $[\text{Ir}(\text{CO})_2(\text{Hdpa})]^+[\text{IrCl}_2(\text{CO})_2]^-$ have also been isolated^{24,25}.

Oro *et al.*⁴³ prepared $[\text{IrI}(\text{TFB})_2]$ and $[\text{IrI}(\text{TFB})(\text{phen})]$ by the metathesis of the corresponding chlorides. Several cationic tetra-coordinated iridium(I) complexes stabilised by diolefins and mono(Q) or bidentate (N-N) *N*-heterocycles are known. The general synthetic route involves the displacement of CH_3CN in $[\text{Ir}(\text{COD})(\text{CH}_3\text{CN})_2]\text{BF}_4/\text{ClO}_4$ in ether with stoichiometric quantities of Q/N-N.

Crabtree *et al.*⁴⁴⁻⁴⁷ isolated $[\text{Ir}(\text{COD})(\text{py})\text{P}(\text{Pcy}_3)]\text{PF}_6$ and this has been shown to be an active hydrogenation catalyst for olefins. Further, the complex is a superior catalyst for the selective hydrogenation of steroids, according to Suggs *et al.*²⁷. Uson *et al.*³⁰ studied the catalytic activity of complexes of the type $[\text{Ir}(\text{COD})\text{Q}_2(\text{N}-\text{N})]\text{BF}_4/\text{ClO}_4$ (Q = substituted py or Qn; N-N = biden-

tate N-heterocycle) for the hydrogen transfer from isopropanol to acetophenone and cyclohexene. In these hydrogen transfer reactions it has been demonstrated that the cationic complexes with bidentate nitrogen heterocycles give rise to systems which are more active than the ones containing monodentate heterocycles. Watson and Ziesel⁸ have recently described homogeneous photo-catalytic systems for the production of hydrogen and carbon monoxide from formate based on photo-active mixed ligand iridium(III) species. These cationic complexes correspond to the molecular formula $[\text{Ir}(\text{N}-\text{N})(\text{C}_5\text{Me}_5)(\text{X})]^+ \text{Y}^-$ ($\text{X}, \text{Y} = \text{Cl}, \text{CF}_3\text{SO}_4, \text{H}, \text{BPh}_4$; $\text{N}-\text{N} = \text{bipy}$ or subst. phen) and have been isolated from the precursor complex $[\text{IrCl}_2(\text{C}_5\text{Me}_5)_2]$ and reported to be effective catalysts for the photochemical water gas shift reaction as well.

A water-soluble cationic complex $[\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{Me}_5\text{Ir}^{\text{III}}(\text{biimztH}_2)\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}$ has been synthesised as a yellow species by stirring $[\eta^5\text{-C}_5\text{Me}_5\text{IrCl}_2]_2$ with two equivalents of biimztH₂ in DMF for 5 h under an inert atmosphere. The complex has been found to display a broad absorption band around 420 nm in its electronic spectrum which is ascribed to metal \rightarrow ligand charge transfer transition. The fast atom bombardment mass spectrum of the complex displays molecular ion peaks as well as the expected isotopic profile. Further, it exhibits a fragmentation peak corresponding to the loss of a coordinated chloride. Such a behaviour has indicated the potential use of this coordinated site in catalytic reactions. Single crystal structure analysis of the complex³¹ (6) has revealed a characteristic three-legged 'piano-stool' arrangement with open angles $\text{Cl}-\text{Ir}-\text{N}(1)$ 85.4°, $\text{Cl}-\text{Ir}-\text{N}(2)$ 85.6° and $\text{N}(1)-\text{Ir}-\text{N}(2)$ 76.0° comparable to those observed in the bipy analogue. The $\text{Ir}-(\text{C}_5\text{Me}_5)$ (mean) and $\text{Ir}-\text{Cl}$ distances are 178.2 and 239.4 pm respectively. The $\text{Ir}-\text{N}(1)$ and $\text{Ir}-\text{N}(2)$ distances have been found to be 210.2 and 211.2 pm.

Oro *et al.*⁴³ isolated several β -diketonate complexes of the formula $[\text{Ir}(\beta\text{-diket}-\text{C}^3)(\text{diolefin})(\text{N}-\text{N})]$ (diolefin = TFB or Me₃ TFB; $\text{N}-\text{N} = \text{bipy}$, phen; β -diket = acac or subst 1,3 dione) as dark coloured solids by the stoichiometric addition of *N*-heterocycle to $[\text{Ir}(\beta\text{-diket})(\text{diolefin})]$ in ether under

stirring conditions. The oxidative addition of I₂ to $[\text{Ir}(\text{acac}-\text{C}^3)(\text{TFB})(\text{phen})]$ or $[\text{Ir}(\text{TFB})(\text{phen})]\text{ClO}_4$ results in the formation of *trans* or *cis* isomers.

The *trans*-isomer $[\text{IrI}_2(\text{phen})-(\text{TFB})]^+$ (7) has been structurally characterised by X-ray diffraction method. The complex is pseudo-octahedral with *trans* iodines, the metal-ligand distances being 274.1 and 275.7 pm. The phen ring makes an

angle of 87.3° with the plane passing through the olefinic bonds. These Ir-I distances are longer than those observed in a related *trans*-diiodo carbomethoxy Ir^{II} complex $[\text{IrI}_2(\text{COOCH}_3)(\text{CO})-(\text{bipy})]$ viz. 267.2 and 268.4 pm. The I-Ir-I 160.43° in the phen complex is distorted from the ideal value of 180°, probably due to steric restrictions imposed by the hydrogen atoms of the TFB moiety. The Ir^{III}-N distances of 207.2 and 209.0 pm are comparable to Ir^{II}-N distances of 211.1 and 209.7 pm observed in $[\text{Ir}(\text{acac}-\text{C}^3)(\text{COD})(\text{phen})]^+$ despite the lower oxidation state of the metal ion in the latter complex.

Oro *et al.*²⁴ also observed that the *N*-heterocycle Hdpa and its deprotonated form are very useful in the syntheses of several neutral cationic and binuclear complexes.

Carbonyl complexes :

The general procedure for the synthesis of mononuclear Ir^I carbonyl species consists in the bridge cleavage of [Ir₂(μ-X)₂(CO)₄] (X = Cl, Br, I, CH₃O, CH₃COO) with *N*-heterocycles in CH₂Cl₂ or a suitable solvent. The number of ν_{CO}s of the resultant complex is suggestive of the *cis* or *trans* disposition of the carbonyls around the metal ion. Table 3 compiles a diverse spectrum of neutral or ionic carbonyls isolated by various workers.

TABLE 3—MONONUCLEAR NEUTRAL OR IONIC COMPLEXES CONTAINING MONO- OR BIDENTATE *N*-HETEROCYCLES

Type	<i>N</i> -Heterocycle Q/(N-NH)/N-N	X L	ν _{CO} cm ⁻¹	Ref.
[Ir(CO)(N-N)X]	bipy	Cl	1 996	33
	aQn	—	2 000 2 050	56
[Ir(CO) ₂ L ₂ Q]	dmpyzt	PPh ₃	1 975, 1 964	48
	dmpyzt		1 954, 1 971	
	bifmpyzt		1 985, 1 962–1 981	
[Ir(CO) ₂ XQ]	py	Cl	2 070, 2 013	49
	pdz	Cl	2 066, 2 049 (solid) 2 070, 2 000 (CH ₂ Cl ₂)	
	napy	Cl	2 068, 2 005	
	<i>N</i> -mimdz		2 004, 2 082	22
	PhCH ₂ imdz	Cl	1 986, 2 070	
	pyz, Qnx, Phz	Cl	1 985–2 090	34
	phen	Cl	1 990, 2 070	
[Ir(CO) ₂ (N-N)]	bimzt	—	2 068 2 000	50
[Ir(CO) ₂ (N-NH)]	<i>a</i> -pybztH		2 072, 2 046 2 018, 2 009	29
	biimztH	—	2 000, 2 068	73

Jeter⁵¹ isolated *cis*-[Ir(CO)₂Clpy] as iridescent green crystals by the chloro-bridge splitting of [Ir₂(μ-Cl)₂(CO)₄] with py. Similar reaction with bipy in dichloromethane affords orange-red crystals. Such square-planar complexes with sterically undemanding ligands have importance as anisotropic materials with one-dimensional conducting properties along the stacking axis³³. The first liquid crystals containing iridium synthesised by Esteruelas *et al.*⁹ through the carbonylation of [IrCl(COD)(pmaa)] are the dicarbonyls corresponding to the composition [IrCl(CO)₂(pmaa)] (pmaa =

NC₅H₄CH=N-C₆H₄OC_nH_{2n+1}; *n* > 5). Two intense ν_{CO} bands observed around 2 050 cm⁻¹ are characteristic of *cis*-orientation of the carbonyls. The complexes are mesomorphic although derived from nonmesogenic ligands.

Oro *et al.*²⁴ obtained a dark green coloured ion-pair carbonyl complex [Ir(CO)₂(dpa)]⁺[IrCl₂(CO)₂]⁻ by bubbling CO through a suspension of [Ir(μ-Cl)(COD)]₂ in presence of Hdpa in CH₂Cl₂ followed by ether addition. *Trans*-[IrCl(CS)(PPh₃)₂] undergoes substitution reaction with bzIH in dichloromethane in presence of KOH to yield [Ir(bzt)(CS)(PPh₃)₂]⁵².

Complexes of the composition [IrX(CO)₂(bbzlH₂py)] (X = Cl(brown), Br(red)) have been synthesised⁵³ by refluxing the carbonylated solution of the hexahaloiridate in 2-methoxyethanol with the heterocycle. These complexes are found to be non-electrolytes in DMF. A single intense peak around 2 000 cm⁻¹ (KBr) in the ir spectrum of these species is suggestive of the *trans* disposition of the carbonyls around the metal. A five-coordinate stereochemistry with the *N*-heterocycle functioning as a chelating bidentate has been proposed. The complex [Ir(α-pybzt)(COD)] undergoes displacement of COD by CO to yield a *cis*-dicarbonyl derivative²⁹.

The crystal structure of [Ir₂(CO)(bipy)-(COOCH₃)] has been determined by Albano *et al.*⁵⁴. The crystal consists of a packing of discrete monomeric units in which the metal atom displays a distorted octahedral configuration with two iodines at the *trans*-positions. The ∠IrI = 176.7° seems to be distorted from the ideal value of 180° as a consequence of short intermolecular contacts separating the halogen atoms. Expectedly, the two Ir-C distances are different. The longer bond (205 pm) connects iridium with *sp*² hybridised carbon of carbomethoxy group. Owing to the relative rotation of the pyridine ring with respect to the other⁵⁵, the chelate ring is not planar, the distortion arises from the repulsive interaction of the δ-hydrogen atoms of the bipy ring. The observed bond distances in complex **8** are rationalised by invoking the presence of an angulated hydrogen bond.

Bi- and polynuclear complexes

Homonuclear heterocycle bridged binuclear complexes :

The general procedure for the syntheses of diolefin containing binuclear complexes bridged by exobidentate *N*-heterocycle(s) involves the halo/methoxy bridge cleavage of $[\text{Ir}(\mu\text{-X})(\text{COD})]_2$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}, \text{CH}_3\text{O}$) in a suitable organic solvent with an *N*-donor ligand. Pyrazolate derivatives, pyrazines, imidazoles, biimidazoles and benzimidazoles are important classes of bridging ligands.

Pyrazolyl bridges : The pyrazolyl bridged iridium(I) complexes have been identified as a novel class of bimetallics^{57,58} whose chemistry combines a number of remarkable features. Bushnell *et al.*⁶¹ demonstrated the versatility of η^2 -pyrazolyl group as a bridging ligand, which can straddle an unusually wide range of intermetallic separation to hold the two adjacent metal centres in a chemically extremely stable configuration.

$[\text{Ir}(\mu\text{-pyzt})(\text{COD})]_2$ (**9**) has been isolated as a purple solid by reacting $[\text{Ir}(\mu\text{-Cl})(\text{COD})]_2$ with pyrazole in presence of Et_3N . Complex **9** forms 1 : 1 adducts^{59,60} with hfby, dmad and *o*-chloranil in THF. The hfby and dmad containing complexes have an Ir–Ir bond length of 262.3 and 263.3 pm respectively (Table 4). Complex **9** also undergoes oxidative addition with X_2 ($\text{X} = \text{Br}, \text{I}$) to give either 1 : 1 or 1 : 2 adducts. With MeI, it affords a 1 : 1 adduct (**10**); the latter has an Ir–Ir distance of 311.2 pm and the corresponding adduct with I_2 has an intermetallic separation of 308.5 pm. The kinetics of MeI addition to pyrazolyl bridged dimers has been studied by Brost *et al.*⁶⁴.

Reaction of $[\text{Ir}(\text{COD})(\mu\text{-Cl})]_2$ with fpyzt in THF/ Et_3N yields a purple pink complex $[\text{Ir}(\text{COD})(\mu\text{-fpyzt})]_2$ ⁶¹ which surprisingly does not show any reactivity towards hfby, dmad, I_2 or MeI. On the other hand, treatment of $[\text{Ir}(\text{COD})(\mu\text{-Cl})]_2$ with a mixture of pyztH and fpyztH in THF/ Et_3N results in the formation of symmetrical dimers $[\text{Ir}(\text{COD})(\mu\text{-pyzt})]_2$, $[\text{Ir}(\text{COD})(\mu\text{-fpyzt})]_2$ as well as the purple coloured bridged diiridium(I) unsymmetrical complex $[\text{Ir}_2(\text{COD})_2(\mu\text{-pyzt})(\mu\text{-fpyzt})]$; the last one was purified by fractional crystallisation. Displacement of the bridging fpyzt occurs in the unsymmetrical dimer when treated with hfby to produce purple crystals of **11** in which one of the iridium centres is terminally coordinated by 1,3,5,6- η - C_8H_{11} unit.

X-Ray crystal structure analysis of **11** indicates an Ir–Ir distance of 285 pm. The reaction of $[\text{IrCl}(\text{COD})(\text{Nmimdz})]$ with MeLi affords a metallated complex⁶² (**12**).

Oro *et al.*⁶³ isolated $[\{\text{Ir}(\text{C}_5\text{Me}_5)\}_2(\mu\text{-H})_2(\mu\text{-pyzt})]\text{BF}_4$ (**13**) as dark blue solids by the prolonged refluxing of $[\{\text{Ir}(\text{C}_5\text{Me}_5)_2\}(\mu\text{-OH})_3]\text{-BF}_4 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ with pyrazoles (pyztH, mpyztH or

dmpyztH) in isopropanol. Unequivocal evidence for bridging hydrogens in the complex stems from the following observations : (i) The singlet hydride resonance (which varies from -11.81 (pyzt) to -12.41 (dmpyzt)), (ii) short Ir–Ir distance of 266.3 pm and (iii) small Ir–N–N angles [Ir(1)N(1)N(2) = 107.1° ; Ir(2)N(2)N(1) = 109.9°]. Pyrazolate anion presents a remarkable flexibility in its exobidentate form of coordination that is fundamental in allowing the adoption of wide range of Ir–Ir separations.

Complex **9** undergoes displacement of diene by CO and PPh₃ to afford [Ir(CO)(PPh₃)(μ-pyzt)]₂ (**14**) as blood red coloured crystals. An alternative

synthetic pathway for the isolation of **14** involves the reaction of Vaska's complex with pyrazolate anion in THF. The crystal structure analysis of the

carbonyl complex reveals an intermetallic separation of 316.2 pm while that in the diene analogue is 321.6 pm (Table 4). Complex **14** serves

TABLE 4—METAL-METAL DISTANCE IN BINUCLEAR IRIDIUM COMPLEXES

Complex	Ir–Ir(pm)
[Ir(COD)(μ-pyzt)] ₂	321.6
[Ir(COD)(μ-pyzt)] ₂ hfby	262.3
[Ir(COD)(μ-pyzt)] ₂ dmad	263.3
[Ir(COD)(μ-pyzt)] ₂ .CH ₃ I	311.2
[Ir(COD)(μ-mfmpyzt)] ₂	307.0
[Ir(COD)(μ-pyzt)] ₂ .I ₂	308.5
[Ir(COD)(μ-pyzt)(μ-hfby)]	285.0
[Ir(CO)(PPh ₃)(μ-pyzt)] ₂	316.2
[Ir(CO)P(OPh) ₃ I(μ-3,5-dmpyzt)] ₂	268.8
[Ir(CO)(PPh ₃)(μ-PH ₂)] ₂	255.4
[{Ir(CO)(PPh ₃) ₂ Cl(μ-4, Cl-pyzt)] ₂	273.7
[Ir(CO) ₂ (μ-pyzt)] ₂	350.2
[Ir(CO) ₂ (μ-3,5-dmpyzt)] ₂	324.5

as a homogeneous hydrogenation catalyst for the conversion of polyacetylene to styrene and ethyl benzene^{59,60}.

The carbonyl complex undergoes oxidative addition with X₂ (X = H, Br or I) to afford pale yellow diamagnetic products of iridium(II) dimers [IrX(CO)(PPh₃)(μ-pyzt)]₂ incorporating an Ir–Ir

bond. ^1H and ^{31}P nmr spectral studies have revealed complex **14** to be stereochemically non-rigid in

solution. The geometric arrangement in this complex places each pair of ligands (either CO or PPh_3) mutually *trans* across the metal-metal axis resulting in a dissymmetric structure belonging to the molecular point group C_2 . The most surprising feature of the structure is the degree of fold in the six-membered cyclic cone when it is bent into a boat conformation which brings the two metal atoms to 316.2 pm of each other. The distance is comparable to that in related complexes^{65,66}. The presence of the metal-metal bond has been based on the fact that the complexes display an ultra-violet absorption band in the range 320–385 nm which is comparable with those in related known systems^{67–69}. The complex adds on chlorine to afford **15** in which substitution has also occurred at the pyrazolyl group. There has been a marked reduction in the Ir–Ir distance (273.7 pm) as compared to that in the precursor complex and lies in the expected range for Ir–Ir single bond consistent with spin-pairing via bond formation.

Treatment of Ir^{I} carbonyl dimer with MeI produces a bright yellow complex **16**. The oxidative addition product displays resonance signals at -140.5 and -141.8 ppm in its ^{31}P nmr spectrum implying that the phosphine ligands are bonded to two nonequivalent Ir^{II} centres. The oxidative addition of diiodomethane⁷⁰ in dipyrazolyl bridged binuclear complexes of iridium is illustrated in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1. Oxidative addition in dipyrazolyl (N–N) bridged species.

It has been surmised that appreciable catalytic activity of binuclear iridium complexes in hydrogenation reactions is due to short Ir–Ir distances. For example, $[\text{Ir}(\mu\text{-}3,5\text{-Me}_2\text{pyzt}(\text{CO})_2)_2]$ which possesses an Ir–Ir bond length of 324.5 pm, has shown a significant catalytic activity as compared to $[\text{Ir}(\mu\text{-}3\text{-Mepyzt}(\text{CO})_2)_2]$ and $[\text{Ir}(\mu\text{-pyzt}(\text{CO})_2)_2]$ which possess a longer Ir–Ir distance of 350.2 pm. Further, it has been demonstrated by Brost and Stobart⁷¹ that steric factors in addition to

metal-metal distances can profoundly alter the kinetics of such catalytic reactions.

Imidazolate and biimidazolate bridged bi- and polynuclear complexes : Net *et al.*⁷² observed in the crystal structure analysis of the dark blue coloured planar binuclear complex **17** bridged by imidazole dicarboxylate, a novel stacking which involves 'slipstacked' binuclear pairs and 'inversion related' binuclear pairs, the Ir-Ir distance between each pair being 330 and 336 pm respectively.

Rasmussen *et al.*⁷³⁻⁷⁵ demonstrated that biimzt anion coordinates as a tetradentate ligand bridging two iridium centres in complex **18**.

The complex has been isolated as a microcrystalline solid by the methoxy-bridge

splitting in $[\text{Ir}(\text{CO})_2(\mu\text{-OMe})]_2$ with biimztH₂ in CH₂Cl₂. Carbonylation of **18** affords $[\text{Ir}_2(\mu\text{-biimzt})(\text{CO})_4]$ by the facile substitution of COD by CO as a deep purple air-sensitive solid. On the other hand, the reaction of $[\text{Ir}(\text{CO})_2(\text{acac})]$ with excess of biimztH₂ in CH₂Cl₂ affords a reddish purple solution, which on concentration under argon affords black needles of the air-sensitive tetranuclear complex, $[\text{Ir}_4(\text{CO})_8(\text{biimzt})_2]$ (**19**). Complex **19** undergoes bridge cleavage in presence of HCl to afford biimztH₂ and $[\text{IrCl}(\text{CO})_2]_2$. Similarly, the carbonylation reaction of $[\text{Ir}_2(\text{COD})_2(\text{Tcnbiimzt})]$ or addition of H₂Tcnbiimzt to $[\text{Ir}(\text{CO})_2(\text{acac})]$ gives $[\text{Ir}_4(\text{CO})_8(\text{Tcnbiimzt})_2]$ ²⁸ (**20**). Polynuclear complexes **19** and **20** are unique in that they do not possess Ir-Ir bonds. It is significant that the change of terminal ligand from cycloocta-1,5-diene to carbonyl modifies the electron density on iridium atom that significant changes in molecular geometry such as change in nuclearity are required to stabilise the system. It has been opined by the authors that the bonding configuration of the biimidazole ligand and the overall molecular structure of the complex may depend upon a sensitive balance of ligand properties.

Pyrazine and bipyridyl bridged species : Halesha⁷⁶ synthesised binuclear complexes of the composition $[\{\text{IrCl}(\text{COD})\}_2(\mu\text{-N-N})]$; (N-N) = pyz, bpy, bpe, by refluxing $[\text{Ir}(\mu\text{-Cl})(\text{COD})]_2$ and N-N in acetone under nitrogen atmosphere. The pyrazine complex has been proposed to possess

structure **21** which is based on the chemical similarity with its rhodium analogue⁷⁷ for which X-ray investigation has been carried out.

Bayon *et al.*⁷⁶ demonstrated that the anions 2,3-pyrazine dicarboxylate and 2,5-pyrazine dicarboxylate have marked differences in their dinucleating properties. With the former ligand, the coordinating

Scheme 2

ability to form second chelate is drastically reduced when one chelate has already been formed owing to steric factors. This is a consequence of the repulsive interaction between the two adjacent carboxylate groups. On the other hand, such a steric hindrance does not occur in 2,5-pyrazine dicarboxylate and hence it readily forms dinuclear species **22**. Dinuclear species **23** has been isolated by treating the dimethoxy-bridged dimer in place of the dichloro dimer with 2,3-pdc. Scheme 2 illustrates

the synthetic route for the binuclear iridium(i) complexes. Ir and nmr spectroscopy have been very useful in assigning the geometries of the complexes **22** and **23**. The ir spectrum of **23** is consistent with an unsymmetrical geometry implying the presence of both an in-plane chelate and a twisted chelate for 2,3-pdc ligand. The ¹H nmr spectrum of **23** displays a broad signal for the two heterocyclic protons H₅ and H₆, suggesting a dynamic equilibrium between the in-plane and out-of-plane chelates. On the other hand, dinuclear complex **22** displays a single resonance absorption for H₃ and H₆ protons of the N-heterocycle consistent with a symmetrical structure.

Complexes containing benzimidazoles: Ramaswamy *et al.*²⁶ synthesised trinuclear complexes of the composition $[\text{Ir}(\text{COD})(\mu\text{-Rbz})]_3$ (**24**); (R = H, Me, Et, ⁿ-pr or ⁿ-Bu) by the chloro-bridge splitting of $[\text{Ir}(\mu\text{-Cl})(\text{COD})]_2$ in presence of Et₃N in acetone. In the absence of the deprotonating agent Et₃N, the reaction is arrested at the mononuclear stage, whereas its presence drives the reaction towards trimerisation. Facile substitution of the diolefin by CO occurs to yield the corresponding *cis*-dicarbonyl derivatives. The trinuclear nature of the complexes has been elucidated on the basis of occurrence of three sets of ¹H and ¹³C resonances of the diene and benzimidazole moieties. The deductions are supported by ¹H{¹H} COSY of the complexes.

Complexes containing oxypyridinate bridges: Rodman and Mann⁷⁹ reported the synthesis, structural characterisation and photochemistry of $[\text{Ir}(\text{COD})(\mu\text{-mop})]_2$ and related oxypyridinate complexes.

Heterobinuclear complexes : According to Uson *et al.*²⁹, the treatment of the complex [Ir(α -pybzt)(COD/NBD)] with AuClL [L = PPh₃/P(OMe)₃] or AgClO₄ in presence of L results in the formation of [M^IL(μ -pybzt)Ir(diolefin)] (**25**); M^I = Ag or Au. The diolefin in the above complexes can

be easily substituted by CO to afford the dicarbonyl species. The reaction of [Ir(α -pybzt)(COD)] with AgClO₄ in 2 : 1 mole ratio yields a trinuclear cationic species [CODIr(μ - α -pybzt)Ag(μ - α -pybzt)Ir(COD)] ClO₄ (**26**).

Pinillos *et al.*⁸⁰ reported the synthesis of a number of binuclear complexes containing pyrazolate bridges. A double heterobridged binuclear complex (**27**) reacts with SnCl₂ to yield a triple heterobridged species (**28**).

Oxidative addition of X₂ (X = Cl or Br) to **27** followed by addition 2 moles of SnCl₂ affords **29** whose X-ray structure analysis reveals that the double bridge maintains an Ir–Ir separation of 272.2 pm, which is suggestive of the presence of a single direct metal-metal bond. The distance is comparable with that in [Ir₂(μ -pyzt)₂(CO)₂Cl₂(PPh₃)₂] which has a separation of 273.7 pm (Table 4).

Balch and Cooper⁴⁹ obtained the heterobinuclear complex [(CO)₂ClRh(μ -napy)IrCl(CO)₂] (**30**) as deep blue crystals by reacting [Rh₂(μ -Cl)₂(CO)₄] with [Ir(CO)₂Cl(μ -napy)]₂ in benzene. The heterobinuclear complex displays a band at 465 nm in the electronic spectrum, which is assigned to d₂₂ → π^* transition.

Conclusion : It is evident that considerable information on the chemistry of organoiridium complexes stabilised by *N*-heterocycles has accumulated in the recent past. Syntheses and characterisation aspects continue to attract the attention of chemists, spectroscopists and crystallographers. The structural features of the complexes are very much dictated by the fine tuning of the electronic and steric factors of the *N*-heterocycles. Several mononuclear complexes have made a dent in the area of synthetic chemistry by serving as selective hydrogenation catalysts. The industrial importance of bi- and polynuclear complexes which are expected to

function as multicentred homogeneous/heterogeneous catalysts is yet to be unravelled.

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List of abbreviations

acac	Acetyl acetone
α -pybzIH	α -Pyridylbenzimidazole
α -pybzt	α -Pyridylbenzimidazolate
aQn	8-Aminoquinoline
bbzIH ₂ Bz	1,3-Bis(2-benzimidazolyl)-benzene
bbzIH ₂ py	2,6-Bis(2-benzimidazolyl)-pyridine
β -diket	β -Diketonato
biimztH ₂	2,2'-Biimidazole
bipy	2,2'-Bipyridyl
biq	2,2'-Biquinoline
bithz	2,2'-Bithiazole
bpe	<i>trans</i> -1,2-Bis(4-pyridyl)-ethane
bpel	<i>trans</i> -1,2-Bis(4-pyridyl)-ethylene
bpy	4,4'-Bipyridyl
btfmpyzl	3,5-Bis(trifluoromethyl)-pyrazolate
Bu ^t py	4-t-Butylpyridyl
Chd	η^4 -Cyclohexa-1,3-diene
C ₅ Me ₅	Pentamethylcyclopentadienyl
COD	<i>cis, cis</i> -Cycloocta-1,5-diene
cosy	Correlated spectroscopy
COT	Cycloocta-1,3,5,7-tetraene
dcQn	4,7-Dichloroquinoline
dmad	Dimethyl acetylenedicarbonylate
dmpyzt	3,5-Dimethylpyrazolate
dmnpyzt	3,5-Dimethyl-4-nitropyrazolate
DNMR	Dynamic nmr
dpa	2,2'-Dipyridylamine (deprotonated form)
dpk	Dipyridylketone
dppn	3,6-Bis(2'-pyridyl)pyridazine
epy	2-Ethylpyridine

Et ₃ N	Triethylamine
fpyzt	3,5-Bis(trifluoromethyl)-pyrazolate
Hdpa	2,2'-Dipyridylamine
hfby	Hexafluorobut-2-yne (C ₄ F ₆)
indzH	Indazole
MeI	Methyl iodide
mes	2,4,6-Trimethylphenyl
mid	Methylimidazole
2.mpy	2-Methylpyridine
4.mpy	4-Methylpyridine
mfpzyt	3-Methyl trifluoromethyl-pyrazolate
mop	6-Methyl-2-oxypyridinate
mpyzt	3-Methyl pyrazolate
napy	1,8-Naphthyridine
NBD	bicyclo(2.2.1)hepta-2,5-diene (Norbornadiene)
N-mebzIH ₂ Bz	1,3-Bis(2- <i>N</i> -methyl)benzimidazolylbenzene
N-mebzIH ₂ py	1,3-bis(2- <i>N</i> -Methyl)benzimidazolylpyridine
Nmimdz	<i>N</i> -Methylimidazole
Nmpy	<i>N</i> -Methylpyrrole
nmQn	5-Nitro-6-methylquinoline
Pcy ₃	Tricyclohexyl phosphine
pdz	Pyridazine
PhCH ₂ imdz	Benzylimidazole
Phen	<i>o</i> -Phenanthroline
Phz	Phenazine
Pip	Piperidine
pmaa	4-Pyridyl-methylene-4'-alkoxyaniline (NC ₅ H ₄ -C=N-C ₆ H ₄ -OC _n H _{2n+1}); (<i>n</i> = 2-14)
py	Pyridine
pyz	Pyrazine
pyztH	Pyrazole
Pyzt	Pyrazolate
Qn	Quinoline
Qnx	Quinoxaline
R-bzIH	Alkylbenzimidazole
R-bzt	Alkylbenzimidazolate
SEt ₂	Diethyl sulphide
tcnbiimzt	4,4', 5,5'-Tetracyanobiimidazolate

TFB	5,6,7,7-Tetrafluoro-1,4-dihydro-1,4-ethanonaphthalene (Tetrafluorobenzobarrelene)
THF	Tetrahydrofuran
tpzmm	Tris(pyrazol-1-yl)methane
Vin	Vinyl

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